

Synthesis of 1,2,3-Benzothiadiazine-1,1-dioxide Derivatives and their Pharmacological Properties

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Formation of 4-(Sub)-amino-1,2,3-benzothiadiazine-1,1-dioxide was established by earlier reported base catalysed ring expansion reaction. Products thus obtained, were stable in aqueous alkaline and acidic medium and on alkylation/acylation furnished 4-amino derivative (4, 5) exclusively, instead of 2-N-derivative (3). Preliminary pharmacological screening was done and the results were positive.

During the course of our studies in synthesis of condensed triazines, we reported¹ the unusual formation of 4-amino-substituted-1,2,3-benzothiadiazine-1,1-dioxide (2) by base-catalysed ring expansion reaction. It was therefore thought interesting to study the feasibility of this new rearrangement reaction and to study chemistry and pharmacology of the new compounds synthesised. Various pharmacological properties^{2,3} are associated with this system. With a view to scan the compounds for their possible effects on CNS, these compounds were first subjected to preliminary pharmacological screening.

Various 2-substituted-3-thiosaccharin (1b-f) on reaction with hydrazine hydrate furnished¹ the corresponding 1,2,3-benzothiadiazine-1,1-dioxide (2b-f) (Scheme 1). However,

Scheme 1

when the same reaction was carried out on 1a, 3-hydrazinosaccharin (6) was exclusively formed in almost quantitative yield, instead of the expected 4-amino-1,2,3-benzothiadiazine-1,1-dioxide (2a). Although the formation of 6 was reported⁴ in the same way, the structure of the product was reinvestigated by chemical reactions as the spectral data is insufficient to distinguish properly the two expected products.

The product obtained from reaction of 1a with hydrazine hydrate (either 6 or 2a) on reaction with ethyl

bromoacetate, furnished 7 instead of 2b (Scheme 2), thus confirming the structure as 6. The benzothiadiazines thus obtained have two centres for alkylation or acylation. Literature⁵ indicates that position-2 is more reactive to alkylation and acylation. Several 2-substituted derivatives have been synthesised³ by alkylation using haloalkyls or isocyanates.

Scheme 2

However, in the present course of the studies, it was observed that 4-amino group was preferentially alkylated and acylated. Alkylation was carried out on 2d to furnish 4-aminomethyl derivative (4d) exclusively. Similarly, acylation of 2b and 2d led to the formation of 4-aminoacetyl derivatives 5b and 5d respectively.

The benzothiadiazine compounds (2) were found to be stable in aqueous, alkaline (2 N NaOH) and acidic (2 N HCl) media.

Pharmacology: The compounds were administered intraperitoneally to adult healthy albino rats (100–200 g) of either sex in the form of suspension using Tween-80 as a suspending agent at the dose range 10–100 mg kg⁻¹. All the rats were observed for the effects on their general gross behaviour at 0.5 h interval for 6 h after injecting the com-

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pounds. Results are as follows : for **2b**, **2c** and **5b** mild sedation (100 mg kg⁻¹), sedation increased with concentration (150 mg kg⁻¹), indication of muscle relaxation at 200 mg kg⁻¹; for **2d**, **2e** and **4d** sedation increased from 50 to 200 mg kg⁻¹, loss of muscle tone and grip strength at 100 mg kg⁻¹, signs of abdominal irritation; **2f** and **5d** no effect upto 200 mg kg⁻¹.

M.p.s. are uncorrected. Ir spectra were determined in KBr and pmr spectra using TMS as internal standard. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc.

4-Substituted-amino-1,2,3-benzothiadiazine-1,1-dioxides (2b-f). *General procedure* : To a stirred suspension of the thio compound (**1b-f**; 10 mmol) in ethanol (20 ml), was added a solution of hydrazine hydrate (80%; 0.75 ml, 12 mmol) in ethanol (20 ml) dropwise in 10–15 min at room temperature and further stirred for 1–2 h. Evolution of H₂S gas was observed during the reaction. The solvent was then

TABLE I—M.p. AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2, 4 AND 5*

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	(cm ⁻¹)/δ	
		v _{max}	
2b	142	v _{max} , 3 280, 3 240, 1 730. δ (CDCl ₃) 1.15 (3H, t, CH ₃), 1.68 (1H, s, NHSO ₂ , D ₂ O exchangeable), 3.96 (2H, d, N-CH ₂ , singlet after D ₂ O), 4.05 (2H, q, OCH ₂), 7.18 (1H, t, NHCH ₂ , D ₂ O exchangeable), 7.68–8.18 (4H, m, ArH)	
c	140	v _{max} 3 260, 3 240, 1 750, 1 730. δ (CDCl ₃) 1.5 (1H, s, NHSO ₂ , D ₂ O exchangeable), 3.6 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 3.9 (2H, d, N-CH ₂ , singlet after D ₂ O), 7.0 (1H, t, NHCH ₂ , D ₂ O exchangeable), 7.6–8.3 (4H, m, ArH)	
d	170	v _{max} , 3 220, 3 280, 1 440. δ (CDCl ₃) 2.75 (3H, d, NHCH ₃ , singlet after D ₂ O), 6.1–6.5 (1H, q, NHCH ₃ , D ₂ O exchangeable), 7.5–8.5 (4H, m, ArH)	
e	190	δ (DMSO-d ₆) 1.1. (3H, t, CH ₃), 3.1 (2H, m, CH ₂), 7.7 (1H, t, NHCH ₂ , D ₂ O exchangeable), 8.0–8.6 (4H, m, ArH)	
f	144	v _{max} , 3 160. δ (CDCl ₃) 4.28 (2H, d, CH ₂ , singlet after D ₂ O), 6.7 (1H, t, NH, D ₂ O exchangeable), 7.16–7.36 (5H, m, ArH), 7.56–8.10 (4H, m, ArH)	
4d	160	v _{max} 3 450. δ (CDCl ₃) 2.7 (6H, s, 2 × CH ₃), 7.6–8.4, (4H, m, ArH)	
5b	127	v _{max} , 3 400, 1 745, 1 755, 1 710. δ (CDCl ₃) 1.3 (3H, t, CH ₃), 2.25 (3H, s, COCH ₃), 4.2 (2H, q, CH ₂), 4.35 (2H, s, CH ₂), 7.6–8.6 (4H, m, ArH)	
d	145	v _{max} 3 400, 1 705. δ (CDCl ₃) 2.3 (3H, s, COCH ₃), 3.2 (3H, N-CH ₃), 7.8–8.75 (4H, m, ArH)	

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses.

removed under reduced pressure and the resulting solid was crystallised from EtOH; yields of **2b-f**, 44–69%.

3-Hydrazinosaccharin (6) : To a stirred hot solution (50°) of thiosaccharin (**1a**; 19.9 g, 100 mmol) in ethanol (100 ml), was added a solution of hydrazine hydrate (80%; 7.5 ml, 120 mmol) dropwise in ~10 min and refluxed further for ~30 min. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol-water (50 : 50) mixture, (18.1 g, 91.9%), m.p. 244–46° (Found : C, 42.8; H, 3.7; N, 21.5; S, 16.0. C₇H₇N₃O₂S requires : C, 42.6; H, 3.6; N, 21.3; S, 16.2%); v_{max} 3 360, 3 340–3 320, 1 620 cm⁻¹.

The ester 7 : To a stirred solution of hydrazinosaccharin (**6**; 9.85 g, 50 mmol) in DMF (25 ml), was added dropwise ethyl bromoacetate (9.19 g, 55 mmol) in ~10 min at room temperature and further stirred for ~5 h. The reaction mixture was then poured in water and allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (8.5 g, 60%), m.p. 188–93° (Found : C, 46.8; H, 4.5; N, 14.7; S, 11.5. C₁₁H₁₃N₃O₄S requires : C, 46.6; H, 4.6; N, 14.8; S, 11.3%); v_{max} 3 350, 1 740, 1 635 cm⁻¹; δ(CDCl₃) 1.25 (3H, t, CH₃), 4.3 (2H, q, OCH₂), 4.0 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 4.5–5.2 (1H, br s, NH), 8.0–8.5 (4H, m, ArH).

Formation of 4d : To a solution of **2d** (2.11 g, 10 mmol) in acetone (40 ml), was added 1 N NaOH solution (10.3 ml) and stirred for ~30 min at room temperature. Dimethylsulphate (1.1 ml, 10 mmol) was then added dropwise in ~10 min and then stirred at room temperature for ~3 h. The resulting solid was washed with precooled acetone and crystallised from ethanol, (80%).

Formation of 5b,d : Compound **2 (b,d)** (10 mmol) was refluxed in acetic anhydride in presence of catalytic amount of pyridine for ~6 h. It was then concentrated under reduced pressure and the crude was poured in water and stirred at room temperature for ~3 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (70–75%).

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